

Synthesis and Utilisation of 3-(2'-Hydroxyethyl)-quinolin-2(1*H*)-ones. Part-II^ψ

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Several 3-(2'-hydroxyethyl)quinolin-2(1*H*)-ones were prepared by the photolysis of *N*-aryl-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxamides. The newly reported quinolonyl ethanols were converted to 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines.

In connection with our syntheses of furo-¹⁻³, thieno-⁴, selenolo-⁵, tellurolo-⁶ and 1*H*-pyrrolo[2,3-*b*]quinolines⁷, we needed several 3-(2'-hydroxyethyl)quinolin-2(1*H*)-ones (**2**) as starting materials. Recently we have reported⁹ the chemical as well as photolytic one-step synthesis of these compounds (**2**) from *N*-aryl-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxamides (**1**)⁸. Chemical method involves the reaction of **1** with a Lewis acid like anhydrous aluminium chloride and other involves a photochemical rearrangement.

Previously, compounds **2a-g** were prepared by both the methods and it was reported already that the photolytic method gave the compounds invariably in higher yields⁹. Now we have extended the work to prepare compounds **2h-w**(1) from the corresponding carboxanilides (**1h-w**) by photolysis. This included several hitherto unreported quinolone alcohols.

Interestingly, in the photolysis of nine *ortho*-substituted anilides (**1j-p**, **r** and **t**) we did not observe any eliminative photocyclisation, the corresponding quinolone alcohols (**2j-p**, **r** and **t**) were obtained as major products in all the cases. This is in agreement with our previous observation that compounds **2e-g** did not undergo the eliminative photocyclisation⁹. In the case of *meta*-substituted anilides (**1u-w**), the photocyclisation could be visualised to occur in two ways, that is to form

the mixture of corresponding 5- and 7-substituted quinolonyl ethanols, e.g. with **1v**, a mixture of two alcohols viz. 7-methoxy- and 5-methoxy-2-quinolone-3-ethanols (**2v** and **v**(1)) resulted.

The newly prepared quinolonyl alcohols, were converted into the corresponding 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines (**3**) by reacting with PPA. The hitherto unknown dihydrofuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines reported here-with are **3h**, **k**, **f**, **p**, **q** and **r**. Reaction of mixture of 5- and 7-substituted quinolonyl ethanols with PPA gave the mixture of the corresponding 5- and 7-substituted 2,3-dihydrofuro[2,3-*b*]quinolines. Of these two isomers, only 7-substituted derivatives, viz. **3u**, **v** and **w** could be separated in the pure state.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Boetius microheating table and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer, ¹H-nmr spectra on Hitachi R-600 spectrometer and mass spectra on a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer RMV-6E spectrometer.

N-Aryl-4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxamides⁸ (**1**): A mixture of 4,5-dihydrofuran-3-carboxylic acid (0.1 mol) and purified thionyl chloride (0.2 mol) was heated on a steam-bath at 40-50° till the solution

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	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴
a	H	H	H	H
b	H	CH ₃	H	H
c	H	Cl	H	H
d	H	H	-CH=CH-CH=C	
e	H	H	H	CH ₃
f	H	H	H	Cl
g	H	H	H	OCH ₃
h	H	Br	H	H
i	H	OCH ₃	H	H
j	OCH ₃	H	H	OCH ₃
k	OCH ₃	Cl	H	OCH ₃
l	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃
m	Cl	H	H	OCH ₃
n	Cl	H	H	CH ₃
o	H	H	Cl	CH ₃
p	H	Cl	H	Cl
q	H	Cl	Cl	H
r	H	H	Cl	Cl
s	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H
t	H	H	H	COOCH ₃
u	H	H	Cl	H
u(i)	Cl	H	H	H
v	H	H	OCH ₃	H
v(i)	OCH ₃	H	H	H
w	H	H	CH ₃	H
w(i)	CH ₃	H	H	H

was complete (3 h). Excess thionyl chloride was distilled off, the residue taken up in benzene (50 ml) and then slowly added to a well-cooled mixture of aniline (0.1 mol) and pyridine (0.1 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml). After the addition was over, it was allowed to stand for 30 min and then poured

into ice-water. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and recrystallised from a suitable solvent (yields 50–84%) (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Compd no	Mp (°C)** Found/(lit)	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)
1h	194-95 (194-95) ^a	1 125, 1 640, 3 285
i	140-41 (140-41) ^b	1 130, 1 640, 3 450
j	103-04	1 130, 1 630, 3 365
k	144-46	1 130, 1 635, 3 350
l	188-90 (189-90) ^a	1 125, 1 620, 3 285
m	105-09	1 120, 1 620, 3 285
n	184-85 (184-85) ^a	1 130, 1 630, 3 290
o	166-68 (167-68) ^a	1 135, 1 650, 3 240
p	168-70	1 130, 1 630, 3 300
q	155-57	1 125, 1 635, 3 350
r	111-13	1 130, 1 630, 3 360
s	95-97 (96-97) ^a	1 130, 1 630, 3 350
t	158-60	1 100, 1 640, 3 250
u	138-39 (139-40) ^b	1 130, 1 640, 3 450
v	148-49 (148-49) ^b	1 130, 1 640, 3 450
w	143-45 (144-45) ^b	1 125, 1 635, 3 250

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses, nmr spectra **1m** δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 2.95 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 4.6 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 3.9 (3H, s), 6.7–7.3 (3H, m), 7.65 (1H, br s), 8.5 (1H, d), **1q** δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) 2.89 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 4.5 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 7.2–7.7 (3H, m), 7.95 (1H, d), 9.0 (1H, br s), **1t** δ (CDCl₃) 2.9 (2H, t, *J* 9 Hz), 4.47 (2H, t, *J* 9 Hz), 3.75 (3H, s), 6.7–7.3 (3H, m), 7.7 (1H, d), 8.5 (1H, d), 10.6 (1H, br s)

Solvent for crystallisation C₆H₆ for **1h–o, **s**, **u–w**, C₆H₆-CHCl₃ for **p–r**, CHCl₃ for **t**
^aRef. 10 ^bRef. 8

3-(2'-Hydroxyethyl)quinolin-2(1H)-ones⁹ (**2**): A solution of furan 3-carboxanilide (**1**; 0.5 g) in dry methanol (300 ml) was placed in a quartz tube, purged with oxygen free nitrogen for 15 min and then irradiated in a Rayonet 208 preparative photoreactor using 253.7 nm light for 20–24 h until

tlc analysis (silica gel/chloroform containing a few drops of ethyl acetate) showed the absence of spot corresponding to **1**. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was placed in a silica gel (20 g) column. The product was eluted with chloroform-ethyl acetate (1 : 1), the eluate was evaporated under reduced pressure and the residue was recrystallised (yields 62–79%) (Table 2).

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2*

Compd no	M P (°C)** Found/(lit)	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)
2 h	175-83d	3 300, 1 640
i	172-73 (172-73) ^a	3 260, 1 645
j	176-78 (177-78) ^a	3 325, 1 635
k	203-04	3 300, 1 630
l	173-75 (174-75) ^a	3 280, 1 640
m	211-12 (211-12) ^a	3 300, 1 635
n	202-03 (202-03) ^a	3 300, 1 650
o	226-28 (227-28) ^a	3 300, 1 640
p	212-13	3 300, 1 640
q	204-06	3 320, 1 635
r	194-96	3 300, 1 630
s	213-15 (215-16) ^b	3 320, 1 640
t	176-78	3 375, 1 680, 1 630
u + u(i)	165-70	3 285, 1 640
v + v(i)	210-15	3 300, 1 640
w + w(i)	136-40	3 310, 1 640

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; nmr spectra : **2o** δ (CDCl₃) 2.55 (3H, s), 2.91 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 3.93 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz) 7.18 (2H, br s), 7.73 (1H, s), 9.66 (1H, br s); **2t** δ (CDCl₃) 2.95 (2H, t), 3.95 (2H, t), 4.1 (3H, s), 4.1 (3H, s), 6.8–8.0 (5H, m).

^aSolvent for crystallisation : MeOH for **2h**, **k**; CH₂Cl–MeOH for **i**, **o–w**, CHCl₃ for **j**, **l**, **m**, **n**

^aRef. 3. ^bRef. 11. d : decomposed

2,3-Dihydrofuro[2,3-b]quinolines^{3,11} (**3**) : A mixture of **2** (500 mg) and PPA (prepared from 5 g P₂O₅ and 3 ml H₃PO₄) was heated on a steam-bath for 4 h. Thereafter it was cooled, poured into ice-water and filtered. The clear filtrate was then

basified with ammonia. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel being eluted with suitable solvent (benzene-chloroform) (yields 65–90%) (Table 3).

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Compd no	M p (°C)** Found/(lit)	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)
3f	178-79	1 635, 1 210
h	235-39	1 635, 1 210
k	185-87	1 630, 1 210
p	166-68	1 630, 1 215
q	157-59	1 630, 1 220
r	181-83	1 630, 1 220
u + u(i)	125-30	1 620, 1 200
u	179-80 (178-80) ^a	1 620, 1 200
v + v(i)	106-15	1 625, 1 205
v	124-25 (124-25) ^a	1 625, 1 205
w + w(i)	110-15	1 630, 1 210
w	137-38 (136-37) ^a	1 630, 1 210

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; nmr spectra : **3k** δ (CDCl₃) 3.4 (2H, t, *J* 12 Hz), 4.03 (3H, s), 4.06 (3H, s), 4.7 (2H, t, *J* 12 Hz), 6.8 (1H, s); **8 5** (1H, s); **q** δ (CDCl₃) 3.26 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 4.5 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 7.3 (2H, m), 7.93 (1H, s), **u** δ (CDCl₃) 3.33 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 4.7 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.23 (1H, dd, *J* 8, 2 Hz), 7.75 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz), 7.8 (1H, s); **v** δ (CDCl₃) 3.3 (2H, t, *J* 9 Hz) 4.65 (2H, t, *J* 9 Hz), 3.9 (3H, s), 6.8–7.7 (4H, m); **w** δ (CDCl₃) 3.3 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 4.7 (2H, t, *J* 8 Hz), 7.6 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.17 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.67 (1H, s), 7.8 (1H, s), 2.5 (3H, s).

^aSolvent for crystallisation : C₆H₆ for **3f**, **u + u(i)**, **u**, **v + v(i)**, **v**, **w + w(i)**, **w**; C₆H₆–CHCl₃ for **h**, **k**, CHCl₃ for

p–r
^aRef. 8.

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